

ANALYSIS OF USE OF EPIGRAPHS IN THE NOVEL 'NORTH AND SOUTH' BY ELIZABETH GASKELL AND THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA TO ITS CREATION PROCESS

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Annotation: *In this article, miniscule part of the famous epigraphs utilized by Elizabeth Gaskell in her industrial novel – 'North and South', as well as, aspects of artistic language of the said book are illustrated generally with valid reasons and reliable sources. Because of the unique writing origin of the novel, how it was affected by social media in its initial process is also mentioned briefly.*

Signal words: *Scot poetry, folklore, epigraphs, hymn, social media, 'Household Words'.*

Elizabeth Gaskell made use of astonishingly 51 epigraphs in her novel 'North and South'. These numbers represent she started every chapter of the novel with an epigraph. Although the quotes made mention of are not notoriously famous ones in the literary circle, they are chosen so perfectly that they make beautiful synergies with the title of chapters. Like here:

MEETING AGAIN (ch LI,451)

'Bear up, brave heart! we will be calm and strong; Sure, we can master eyes,

cheek, or tongue, Nor let the smallest tell-tale sign appear She ever was, and is, and will be dear.' RHYMING PLAY. (epigraph),

This chapter features the touching on the inside and not so touching on the outside reunion of the couple secretly in love. The given epigraph can be said to be the perfect description of the palpitation of the heart, tremor of the soul when they come across each other after a long arduous 2 years. Or here:

ALONE! ALONE! (ch XLII,374)

'When some beloved voice that was to you Both sound and sweetness, faileth suddenly, And silence, against which you dare not cry, Aches round you like a strong disease and new— What hope? what help? what music will undo That silence to your senses?' MRS. BROWNING (epigraph)

In this chapter, the employment of the title and the epigraph alone makes sure that the readers figure out what is going to conspire in the upcoming events, what the whole chapter is about, as well as, confer feelings of utter loneliness.

The choice of epigraphs aside, the origin of the epigraphs are also worth discussing. The Author makes use of relevant folkloristic quotes like the one in the very first chapter:

Woo'd and married, and a' ,

This is from a traditional Scottish song which is sung before the wedding of the bride(also known as The Bride Came' Out O' The Byre):

Woo'd and married, and a', Married, and woo'd, and a! And was she nae very weel off, That was woo'd, and married and a'? Or:

And it's hame, hame, hame, Hame fain wad I be'

This one is also from Scottish poetry by Allan Cunningham that was taken as an epigraph for the chapter 'HOMESICKNESS'. This poem which evokes the pain of the exile who wishes to be back home – in the case of the novel's heroine, as a result of abandoning the home she called where she lived less than a few years at most.

Consequently, quotes in the novel is not limited to folklores and Scot poetry. The epigraph of the chapter 'DOUBTS AND DIFFICULTIES', for instance, is a piece from the Hymn:Father, I know that all my life:

'I ask Thee for a thoughtful love, Through constant watching wise, To meet the glad with joyful smiles, And to wipe the weeping eyes; And a heart at leisure from itself To soothe and sympathize.' ANON.

Skillfully interpolating these various epigraphs according to the titles is something that demands of the Author immense knowledge. Certainly, this one article is not enough to wholly cover the entireship of the epigraphs and the quotes employed in the novel, making it happen requires through investigations of the origins of them. However, just those above alone are able to demonstrate how gracefully the quotes are selected.

The other aspect today's article embraces is the negative influence of social media, specifically the journal 'Household words' have had to 'North and South'. It would honestly be an exaggeration to say it had an actual negative impact over the novel, however, it is an indisputable fact that the novel experienced certain shortcomings due to it. Particularly, the fact is briefed about at the very beginning of the book:

"On its appearance in 'Household Words,' this tale was obliged to conform to the conditions imposed by the requirements of a weekly publication, and likewise to confine itself within certain advertised limits, in

order that faith might be kept with the public. Although these conditions were made as light as they well could be, the author found it impossible to develop the story in the manner originally intended, and, more especially, was compelled to hurry on events with an improbable rapidity towards the close. In some degree to remedy this obvious defect, various short passages have been inserted, and several new chapters added. With this brief explanation, the tale is commended to the kindness of the reader”

‘Beseking hym lowly, of mercy and pite, Of its rude making to have compassion”.

Above, they are basically saying that the novel could be way better if not for the strict deadlines and the urges of some people (like editors?). The book turned out a little worse than the expected, thus, was added additional passages along with extra chapters, is what Elizabeth Gaskell wants to convey. ‘Household words’ is a weekly journal, consequently, the Author had to make for it in rapidity which slightly affected the novel's original plot. However, this is not a problem unsolvable in the current era of social media.

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